

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Bansal****FIRST NAME: Barkha****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is less than 10%.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The purpose of a dissertation prospectus is to:

- Determine the topic of the dissertation.
- Provide students the ability to understand the dissertation.
- Provide an opportunity to the supervisory committee to review research questions.¹**
- Invite students to forward research proposals.

2. The sampling section of the research method helps in understanding:

- Method of selecting interview questions.

¹ John P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 3.

- Method of selecting participants.**²
- Analyse the size of the demography sample.
- Purpose of the dissertation.
3. Choose the most appropriate structure for a written essay:
- Introduction, body, conclusion.**³
- Introduction, literature review, body, conclusion
- Abstract, body, conclusion.
- Introduction, research methods, body, conclusion.
4. During paraphrasing, it is essential to:
- Present the ideas of others in our own words.**⁴
- Use the author's style of language.
- Present the language of the author as it is.
- Use direct quotes from the other work.
5. The Data collection method is about:
- Collecting information about the Dissertation.
- Collecting information about past studies

² Ibid., 42.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 9.

⁴ Ibid., 12.

Process of describing tools, instruments, and procedures of collecting data.⁵

The Process of including collected data in the research.

6. It is important to bear in mind when thinking about and formulating each of your conclusions that they must be logically tied to one another because:

There should be some sort of consistency among your conclusions.⁶

There has to be a correlation with your research question

There should be counter-arguments in the conclusion

There has to be sufficient evidence to conclude.

7. Foreign words and phrases used in English text should be italicised because:

It is essential for the non-native speakers.⁷

It is easier to spot the use of foreign words

It is essential to explain foreign expressions

It is easier for the author to explain with foreign words.

8. A colon is most often used to indicate:

The connection of sentences

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Sage Publication: Columbia University, 2008), 3.

⁶ Ibid., 679.

⁷ European Commission. *English Style Guide: A handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. (European Union, 2016), 48.

An expansion, qualification, or explanation that is about to follow.⁸

An explanation of the earlier sentence

The connection of multiple paragraphs.

9. When planning the first draft of a dissertation, it is important to:

Create an outline and structure of the research.⁹

Create multiple research questions.

Provide the potential or possible conclusion.⁸

Narrow down the research questions.

10. The primary reasons for citing the sources are:

Explain the uses of references.

Give credit to the author of the sources.¹⁰

To give a constructive look at the dissertation.

Provide the list of authors referred to.

⁸ Ibid. 8.

⁹ Kate L Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 69.

¹⁰ Ibid., 139.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.